

A study on the normal charging controller system for the solar energy Pros and Cons

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Abstract

Renewable Energy System is now becoming the important alternative to the conventional energy system. This is due to the fact that the renewable energy resource is environment friendly and causes zero pollution to the atmosphere. In addition to this the conventional energy is suffering from fossil fuel for the production. Due to this more and more encouragement is given to the renewable energy system. One such renewable energy system is the solar energy system which is gaining more and more market in India. This is also called a clean and green energy system. Every solar energy system is comprising of a set solar panel, charge control system, energy storage system and inverter system. Here the role of solar charging system is very important. This system should accept solar energy from the solar panel and supply it to either storage system or inverter system. The amount of energy from solar varies from time to time which depends upon the angle of solar incident. Similarly the load for the inverter changes from time to time. The variation in the solar energy and load requirement has to be balanced by the charge controller. The objective of this paper is to study the performance of the various solar charge controller and suggestion to improve the efficiency of the same. Here the available solar charge controllers are studied and performance is noted and improvement suggestion is given. The outcome of this paper is the performance of the current charge controllers, special features of the same and new proposal for the performance improvement.

Keywords: Solar charge controller, Solar energy, Charge controller performance, Renewable energy.

Introduction

The solar energy system uses the photon from the sunlight and converts the photon into electrical energy using silicon. [1] About 47% of the photon from the sun reach the earth's atmosphere. Rest of the energy is either reflected by the cloud or absorbed by the dust particles. [2] This results in variation in solar energy from time to time due to the changes in the atmosphere. The 12V solar panel consists of 36 solar cells which exposed to sunlight. These cells are manufactured using silicon which emits electron when it comes in contact with the photon from the sun light. Each cell thus produces 0.5V of potential difference during sunlight. The amount of current generated depends upon the size of each cell. If the cell is large the current will be more whereas if the cell is smaller then the current will be less. So the total power of the solar panel depends on the product of the amount of voltage difference and the current. [3] There are varieties of solar panel available with different power ratings. These solar panels are available with either 12V or 24V voltage differences. The charging voltage and charging current solely depends upon the amount of sunlight which falls on the panel. [4] This results in continuous variations in the charging of the battery backup. This results in need of charging controller to be installed to balance the solar charging to the battery backup to maintain the long life of the battery. [5]

The 12V solar panel produces a potential difference of 18V during the peak output and decreases gradually when the intensity of sunlight decreases. The potential difference and the current directly proportional to the incident photon on the surface of the panel.[6] This panel is used to charge a battery of 12V. A charge controller is used to control the incoming solar energy to charge the battery. Here the problem is the input voltage of 18V from the panel which gets reduced to 12V with the help of a charge controller. The difference in the voltage gets wasted into heat. This heat is a waste. A solar panel which is used to charge 24V battery (2 batteries in series) has an output of 36V potential difference out of which the charge controller reduces the voltage to 24V. Normally when the solar energy is used at a large scale the panels are set up in a series manner to get the voltage of 240V. The charge controller gives the output to be at 240V when it receives 360V as input voltage. A difference of 120V is wasted in this process.

The solar energy system uses three different type of charge controllers namely

- A simple single stage or two stage controllers.

- A PWM charge controllers.

- Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) charge controllers.[7]

A Simple Charge Controller: In the case of simple charge controller the input voltage from the solar panel undergoes a simple one or two stage shunt transistor with a zener diode which decides the regulated output voltage i.e. 12V. [8] When the desired voltage of the battery backup is reached then the charge controller simply shorts the panel voltage and thus the energy produced later will be given to a protective diode as well as the resistance load to avoid the short circuit for the panel. This is the reason why the charge controller is not in use.

A PWM Charge Controller: In this case a modified charge controller is used to charge the battery backup as well as to protect the solar panel from short circuit. Here a new technique is used where in the charge controller used a micro controller chip which charges the battery bank using PWM method. In this method the battery will be under boost charging until the

battery voltage reaches a reference voltage (14.5 V for 12V battery). After that a small pulse will be trickled to maintain the battery voltage. [9]

A MPPT Charge Controller: This is an improved charge controller which improves the efficiency of the solar energy production as well as utilization. This technology uses MPPT algorithm which converts the input solar DC energy into output AC energy. This AC energy is reconverted into DC energy to provide the energy required to the battery. This algorithm has boost converter as well as buck converter. [10]

Objective:

The objective of this paper is to study the performance of three types of solar charge controller and compare the performances and derive at a model which overcomes the problems observed in the above three charge controllers.

Methodology:

The study of individual charge controller is done with the block diagram, performance and the drawbacks of the same. Then the suggestion over the improvement over the charge controller to get rid of the drawbacks is given. The analysis of the proposed model is done. Then the conclusion is given.

A Simple Charge Controller: The block diagram of a simple single stage or two stage solar charge controller is as shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1: A simple one or two stage solar charge controller

As mentioned in the figure a shunt transistor acts as a charge controller for the solar input towards the battery. The shunt transistor takes a reference voltage with the help of a zener diode. This reference voltage allows the transistor to charge the battery until the reference voltage is reached. Once the battery voltage reaches the reference voltage then the transistor stops the battery from charging. Here the input energy from the solar panel passes through the shunt load resistor once the battery is full.

A PWM Charge Controller: More efficient charge controller compared to the simple solar charge controller is PWM charge controller. The block diagram of the same is shown in the figure 2.

Figure 2: A PWM solar charge controller

This is a charge controller wherein depending on the energy stored in the battery bank the charging pulses will have different pulse widths. If the energy stored is less and more charging is required then the pulse width of the charge controller will be large. As the battery stores the energy the pulse width of the controller reduces. Finally when the battery is full a spike pulse will be generated by the controller to maintain the battery voltage. This technique does not allow the battery to overheat and battery life will be improved.

A MPPT Charge Controller: A latest technology in the field of solar charge controller is recently introduced. This technology is called maximum power point tracking (MPPT) controller. The block diagram of the same is as shown in the figure 3

Figure 3: A MPPT Charge Controller.

The main idea behind this charger is to charge the battery bank to the maximum extent. Here a MPPT algorithm is used by the controller which will convert the input solar DC energy into AC energy. This energy is then undergoes either a Buck controller or a Boost controller to transfer every charge to the battery bank or to the DC load.

The New Proposed Model

By studying the performance of three types of the solar charge control a proposed model of the charge controller is introduced wherein the drawbacks of the previous is considered for the increased efficiency of the solar energy.

The simple shunt type single stage or two stage transistor based charge controller is waved off because of its performance during the full battery bank mode.

The MPPT as well as the PWM based charge controller is combined to get more efficiency in solar energy utilization. The energy produced undergoes the MPPT technology to consider all the energy produced during peak hours as well as non peak hours. The PWM charge controller is used to charge the battery optimally. The advantage of using PWM charge controller is it increases the life of the battery bank as the battery bank do not heat during charging. The bubble formation during charging will be reduced.

The new proposed model of the solar charge controller is as shown in the figure 4.

Figure 4: Proposed model of solar charge controller.

Analysis: The performance of all the present solar charge controllers is compared with the proposed model using the table 1.

Table1. The Comparison between the various solar charge controllers.

Sl. No	Parameter	Single stage Shunt transistor	PWM	MPPT	New Proposed Model
1.	Load Short after Battery Charge	Yes	No	No	No

2.	Battery Boiling	More	Less	Less	Less
3.	Battery Life	Less	More	More	More
4.	Trikkle Charging	-	Yes	No	Yes
5.	Buck Charging	-	No	Yes	Yes
6.	Boost Charging	-	No	Yes	Yes
7.	After Charging	Solar Panel may be shorted	Solar energy is wasted	Solar energy is diverted to DC load	Solar Energy can be diverted to both DC as well as AC load

Conclusion: The performance of the different solar charge controller is studied. The major observation is that after full recharge of the battery bank the solar energy is either wasted or the resistive load is connected to the solar panel. This will reduce the life of the solar panel. Even MPPT solar charger diverts the load to Dc load, may not be useful to the commercial applications. The new proposed charge controller is combining the feature of both MPPT as well as PWM. This charger will take the input voltage and current to charge the battery bank by converting the power into the requirement of the battery bank. This proposed charge controller will work in all conditions whether the input voltage is less than the battery voltage or more. In addition to this the charge controller will manage the load both DC as well as AC when battery bank does not require power to charge.

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